

EFFICIENCY OF TRIPHASIC COMPUTED TOMOGRAPHY (CT) SCAN IN FOCAL TUMORAL LIVER LESIONS COMPARING WITH ULTRASOUND

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Abstract

Background: Accurate detection and characterization of focal tumoral liver lesions are essential for guiding clinical management. Ultrasound is widely used as a first-line tool but has limitations in sensitivity and lesion characterization. Triphasic computed tomography (CT) offers multiphase vascular-phase imaging that may improve diagnostic performance.

Objective: To compare the diagnostic efficiency of triphasic CT with conventional ultrasound in the evaluation of focal tumoral liver lesions.

Methods: A prospective comparative diagnostic accuracy study was conducted on 65 patients with focal liver lesions detected on ultrasound. All underwent triphasic CT within two weeks. Final diagnoses were confirmed by histopathology or follow-up imaging. Sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), negative predictive value (NPV), and overall accuracy were calculated for both modalities.

Results: Triphasic CT achieved 100% sensitivity, specificity, PPV, NPV, and accuracy in diagnosing malignant lesions. Ultrasound showed sensitivity of 73.8%, specificity of 95.7%, PPV of 96.9%, NPV of 66.7%, and accuracy of 81.5%. CT also reduced indeterminate cases compared to ultrasound (26.2% vs. 15.4%).

Conclusion: Triphasic CT outperforms ultrasound in characterizing focal tumoral liver lesions and should be considered when ultrasound findings are inconclusive or when malignancy is suspected.

INTRODUCTION

Tumoral liver lesions have a variable prevalence depending on the type and population studied.

Benign focal liver lesions are found in about 15% of hospital patients undergoing ultrasound, with hepatic cysts (5.8%), hepatic hemangiomas

(3.3%), focal nodular hyperplasia (0.2%), and hepatic adenomas (0.04%) being the most common.(1) Incidental focal liver lesions in healthy populations range from 2.3% to 6.2% on ultrasound screening, with about half of these being hemangiomas and a small proportion malignant.(2) Hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC), a common malignant liver tumor, shows an incidence of less than 5 per 100,000 population in northern Europe but can reach 20 per 100,000 in high-risk regions like China and Southeast Asia.(3) Diagnosis relies primarily on imaging modalities such as triphasic CT, which offers high sensitivity and specificity through multiphase contrast enhancement, and ultrasound, which is often used for initial detection and characterization. These imaging techniques help differentiate benign from malignant lesions effectively and guide clinical management.(4).

Liver cancer is a significant issue affecting population health worldwide, and it plays a significant role in morbidity and mortality associated with cancer. These tumors may be generally classified as primary or secondary (metastatic) lesions. Hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) is a primary liver tumor that is often related to chronic liver diseases, including hepatitis B and C, alcoholic liver disease, and non-alcoholic fatty liver disease. (5) Nonetheless, metastatic liver tumors, especially those caused by colorectal, breast, pancreatic and lung cancer, are more common given the fact that the liver is in charge of blood filtration in the system. The timely and proper characterization of focal liver lesions (FLLs) is essential to the enhancement of prognosis and clinical management. Imaging studies can be a critical part of the clinical decision making process and they must give credible data regarding the morphology of the lesions, its vascularity and the existence of any complications in the form of vascular invasion or extrahepatic spread.(6)

Imaging is a key element of identification, characterization, staging, and follow-up of liver tumors. There is a variety of imaging modalities that have particular advantages and limitations. Ultrasound and computed tomography (CT) are

among the most common tools used in assessment of liver lesions.(7) The first-line imaging modality typically used is ultrasound due to its inherent low cost, non-invasiveness, portability, and lack of ionizing radiation. It can be the initial step to any patient with non-specific abdominal symptoms, abnormal liver functions or during a health check-up. Ultrasound can be used to rapidly evaluate the architecture and lesion morphology of the liver and, with Doppler imaging, the pattern of vascular flow. These advantages notwithstanding, ultrasound has prominent limitations, especially in obese patients, when there is excessive bowel gas, or when the lesions are small, isoechoic, or in a deep portion of the liver parenchyma.(8)

Conversely, triphasic CT imaging has taken a central stage in imaging of the liver because of its high spatial resolution, as well as the capability of evaluating the phases of the hepatic vasculature dynamically. A triphasic CT scan is an intravenous contrast medium administration and three-phase scanning (arterial, portal venous, and delayed). (9) A characteristic set of enhancement patterns can be visualized using this temporal imaging sequence, which is important in lesion characterization. As an example, HCC is frequently characterized by an arterial phase hyperenhancement with subsequent washout in portal venous or delayed phases, which may be hard to detect with ultrasound. These dynamic contrast patterns of triphasic CT are very useful to differentiate benign and malignant lesions, various malignant lesions.(10)

The rise in the cross-sectional imaging has been contributing to an upsurge in incidental finding of focal liver lesions that are asymptomatic in many cases. The distinguishment between benign and malignant lesions is a critical step since it directly affects the selection of treatment modalities that can include surgical resection or liver transplantation, systemic chemotherapy, or palliative treatment.(11) Although simple cysts and hemangiomas can usually be detected via ultrasound, ultrasound is less adequate in describing atypical or solid lesions. Moreover, ultrasound is operator-intensive, and so its diagnostic quality depends greatly on the

experience and talent of the sonographer. Such inconsistency highlights the importance of more objective and reproducible imaging methods, particularly when clinical suspicion of malignancy is strong.(12)

Triphasic CT eliminates most of the drawbacks of ultrasound. It provides more precise anatomical and functional detail and allows the identification of non-apparent lesions not seen using ultrasound and a more detailed estimate of the lesion size, internal architecture and position relative to other structures. This is especially necessary in preoperative planning, where proper outlining of the tumor boundaries and vascular invasion may determine the possibility and the volume of surgical excision. Furthermore, CT imaging can be reproduced and can be assessed and compared over time, which is essential when tracking the response to treatment or the progression of the disease.(13)

As beneficial as it is, triphasic CT does not come without disadvantages. Ionizing radiation and the utilization of iodinated contrast agents present an added risk of carcinogenesis by radiation and contrast induced nephropathy, especially in patients with pre-existing renal dysfunction. Furthermore, CT scan is more costly compared to ultrasound and it is not accessible easily in every clinical environment especially in resource-constrained environments. Thus, CT imaging should be practiced wisely, and the necessity of high diagnostic accuracy should be accompanied by the risks and expenses of the technique.(14)

Contrast-enhanced ultrasound (CEUS) has been suggested within recent years as an alternative to liver lesion evaluation. CEUS is an imaging technique that is used to measure vascular patterns in real-time, with an imaging dynamic comparable to that of triphasic CT, but without ionizing radiation or nephrotoxic contrast. Although CEUS has a good deal of potential, particularly with respect to distinguishing between HCC and other hypervascular lesions, it is operator-dependent and is not yet universal nor widely accepted as a primary modality. Moreover, CEUS is not always applicable to whole-liver examinations, being confined instead to selected examinations, thus it is not as effective in terms

of staging or surveillance in multifocal or metastatic disease.(15)

Since the clinical significance of effective and efficient diagnosis of focal liver lesions is high, it is of utmost interest to compare the effectiveness of various imaging modalities. In spite of the fact that ultrasound is still frequently employed as a first-line method of diagnosis, it has certain shortcomings in the area of lesion characterization and staging that require the application of more superior imaging methods like triphasic CT. When the results of the ultrasound are not conclusive or indicate a possibility of malignancy, a follow-up triphasic CT scan is usually used to provide more conclusive information on diagnosis. Nonetheless, the efficiency, cost-effectiveness and sensitivity of routinely escalating to CT imaging, particularly in places where healthcare resources are limited, continues to remain debatable.(16)

It is not yet established that triphasic CT and ultrasound are comparatively efficient in detecting and characterizing focal tumoral liver lesions. Although a few studies have indicated that triphasic CT offers better diagnostic outcomes, others have highlighted the usefulness of ultrasound and especially that which is done by skilled operators or supplemented by contrast. Clinical practice also varies between the thresholds to proceed to CT after ultrasound, with this practice often depending on institutional policies and physician preference in addition to patient factors. As a result, we can see the obvious necessity of the evidence-based guidelines that would outline the particular clinical situations when triphasic CT could provide us with the significant diagnostic benefit in comparison with ultrasound.

This thesis will attempt to fill this gap by comparing systematically the diagnostic performance of triphasic CT and ultrasound in the assessment of focal tumoral liver lesions. The research will be based on sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value, negative predictive value, overall diagnostic accuracy, performance measures. Evaluation of these parameters should allow finding the relative strengths and weaknesses of each modality and define their

roles regarding diagnostic algorithm of hepatic tumors.

The evaluation of focal tumoral liver lesions represents a complex and clinically significant challenge that requires the integration of multiple imaging modalities. While ultrasound remains a valuable first-line tool, triphasic CT offers a more comprehensive and reliable approach for lesion characterization and staging. By systematically comparing the efficiency of these two modalities, this thesis seeks to contribute to a more evidence-based and patient-centered approach to liver imaging. The results of the study will have important implications for clinical practice, particularly in guiding the appropriate use of advanced imaging techniques in the diagnosis and management of hepatic tumors.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Saima Hafeez et al. (2012) conducted a study to evaluate the diagnostic accuracy of triphasic spiral computed tomography (CT) in distinguishing benign from malignant focal tumoral liver lesions. The research was carried out at the Radiology Department of Aga Khan University Hospital and the Sindh Institute of Urology and Transplantation, Karachi, over a one-year period from February 2006 to February 2007. A total of 45 patients with radiologically detected focal liver lesions were selected through convenient sampling. Each patient underwent a triphasic CT scan, and the imaging findings were later correlated with histopathological results, which served as the reference standard. The primary goal was to determine the sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), negative predictive value (NPV), and overall diagnostic accuracy of the triphasic CT scan in lesion characterization. The study identified 136 liver lesions in total—11 benign and 125 malignant—based on contrast enhancement patterns. Among the 45 patients, 37 (82.2%) were initially diagnosed with malignant lesions and 8 (17.8%) with benign lesions. Histopathological analysis, however, confirmed 35 cases (77.8%) as malignant and 10 (22.2%) as benign. Based on these comparisons, triphasic CT demonstrated a

sensitivity of 100%, specificity of 80%, PPV of 94.5%, NPV of 100%, and an overall diagnostic accuracy of 95.5%. The findings of Hafeez et al. (2012) support that triphasic CT scanning is a highly effective, non-invasive imaging modality for the accurate differentiation of malignant and benign liver lesions, making it a valuable tool in clinical decision-making and management planning. (12)

Chandra Prakash Ahirwar et al. (2016) conducted a comprehensive study to assess the role of triple-phase computed tomography (CT) in evaluating hepatic lesions. The liver, owing to its essential roles in digestion, detoxification, and its dual blood supply from the hepatic artery and portal vein, is highly susceptible to a variety of pathological conditions, both benign and malignant. Given these vulnerabilities, accurate imaging plays a critical role in timely diagnosis and treatment planning. The primary objectives of the study were threefold: first, to identify and describe the characteristic imaging features of various hepatic lesions using triple-phase CT; second, to differentiate benign from malignant hepatic lesions based on these imaging findings; and third, to correlate the CT results with clinical data, histopathological examination, or post-operative findings in order to determine the diagnostic efficacy of the modality. This cross-sectional study was carried out in the Department of Radiodiagnosis at Gandhi Medical College, Bhopal, Madhya Pradesh, India, and included 100 patients. Each participant underwent a triple-phase contrast-enhanced CT (CECT) scan. The researchers then calculated the accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity of this imaging approach for lesion characterization. The results demonstrated that triple-phase CT is an excellent diagnostic tool for the characterization and in-depth evaluation of hepatic masses. The modality achieved a sensitivity of 91.3%, specificity of 97.8%, positive predictive value (PPV) of 91.3%, and negative predictive value (NPV) of 97.8%, with a statistically significant p-value of less than 0.001 and a kappa value of 0.847, indicating substantial agreement. In the detection of malignant hepatic lesions specifically, triple-phase CT achieved an accuracy of 93%, with sensitivity

and specificity values of 93.3% and 92.5%, respectively, along with a PPV of 94.9% and an NPV of 90.2%. The study concluded that triphasic CT, owing to its high diagnostic accuracy, is invaluable for the confident identification and characterization of hepatic lesions. It plays an indispensable role in distinguishing benign from malignant conditions, thereby guiding appropriate management and surgical planning. Furthermore, it can aid in diagnosing primary malignancies in cases where multiple liver metastases are present from an unknown primary source. (17)

Waseem Zafar et al. (2018) conducted a study to evaluate the role of biphasic and triphasic computed tomography (CT) in diagnosing focal tumoral liver lesions. The research was carried out in the Department of Radiology at Medcare International Hospital and GINUM Cancer Hospital, Gujranwala, between March 11, 2015, and December 2015. A total of 60 patients were included, in whom 60 liver lesions were identified based on distinct enhancement patterns. Of these, 49 lesions (81.67%) were malignant, while 11 lesions (18.33%) were benign. Among the malignant group, 26 patients had multifocal hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC), 15 presented with a single focal lesion of HCC, 5 had secondary metastatic deposits, and 3 were diagnosed with cholangiocarcinoma. The benign group comprised various non-malignant hepatic pathologies. For further analysis, the authors focused on 41 patients either suspected of or diagnosed with HCC, who demonstrated elevated alpha-fetoprotein (AFP) levels and were confirmed to have HCC. The findings reinforced that biphasic and triphasic CT scans are highly valuable, noninvasive imaging modalities. They offer reliable characterization of focal liver lesions, enabling differentiation between benign and malignant masses. This diagnostic precision is crucial for guiding appropriate treatment strategies and improving patient outcomes. (18)

Rohail Akbar et al. (2024) conducted a detailed study to investigate the diagnostic utility of triphasic computed tomography (CT) in characterizing liver lesions initially detected on ultrasonography. Liver disease remains one of the

leading causes of mortality in Pakistan and across Asia, with liver carcinoma ranked among the most prevalent cancers worldwide. Early detection of hepatic malignancies is essential for timely intervention, improved treatment outcomes, and better long-term prognosis. Computed tomography, particularly in its triphasic protocol, allows for imaging at multiple time points following contrast administration—typically during the arterial, portal venous, and delayed phases—providing a dynamic assessment of lesion vascularity. This approach enhances the accuracy of differentiating between benign and malignant hepatic pathologies. The primary objective of this cross-sectional quantitative study was to characterize liver lesions identified on ultrasonography and determine their nature—benign or malignant—among patients presenting to Bilal Hospital, Rawalpindi, Pakistan. Data from 50 patients meeting the inclusion criteria were analyzed. Eligible participants were aged over 30 years; patients below this age, pregnant women, those with contrast allergies, or individuals with abnormal renal function tests were excluded. All patients underwent triphasic CT scanning using a 64-slice scanner. The scans were acquired in the arterial, portal venous, and delayed phases following intravenous contrast administration. Experienced radiologists interpreted the findings, focusing on features such as lesion morphology, enhancement patterns, and associated hepatic changes. The study also documented concurrent conditions including hepatomegaly, cirrhosis, and portal hypertension, as initially suspected on ultrasonography. Data analysis was performed using SPSS version 25, with full adherence to ethical protocols including informed patient consent, privacy, and confidentiality. The results revealed that 28% of the cases involved benign liver lesions. Among these, focal nodular hyperplasia (14%) was the most frequent, followed by hemangiomas (10%) and hepatic cysts (4%). Malignant lesions were significantly more common, observed in 62% of patients. Hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) emerged as the predominant malignancy, accounting for 36% of cases. This was followed by secondary metastatic

lesions (10%), cholangiocarcinoma (8%), and focal hepatic lesions of malignant nature (8%). HCC was the single most frequently identified condition across all participants. The study concluded that both benign and malignant liver lesions are prevalent in patients over 30 years of age, with HCC representing the most common malignancy and focal nodular hyperplasia the most frequent benign lesion. The findings strongly reinforce the indispensable role of triphasic CT in the precise characterization and differentiation of hepatic lesions. By providing high-resolution, phase-specific imaging, triphasic CT enables radiologists and clinicians to make confident diagnostic decisions, thereby guiding optimal treatment strategies, surgical planning, and long-term patient management. (9)

Faiza Jabeen et al. (2022) conducted a cross-sectional study to assess liver diseases using triphasic spiral computed tomography (CT), a widely accepted imaging method for detecting and characterizing both benign and malignant hepatic lesions. Triphasic CT, by capturing images at arterial, portal venous, and delayed phases, enables detailed visualization of vascular patterns and tissue enhancement characteristics. This capability not only improves diagnostic precision but also contributes to reducing morbidity and mortality associated with liver diseases by enabling earlier and more accurate interventions. The study aimed to evaluate liver diseases in real time using triphasic CT imaging. It was carried out at three healthcare facilities—Al-Amin Diagnostic Center, Chattha Hospital, and Gondal Hospital. Prior to undergoing the CT procedure, each participant provided written informed consent. A total of 65 patients meeting the inclusion criteria were examined. All patients had previously been diagnosed or suspected of having various hepatic conditions, and their triphasic CT scan findings were analyzed in detail. The mean patient age was 53.5 years, with an age range between 30 and 84 years. The study population consisted of 39 males (60%) and 26 females (40%). The most frequently observed findings included hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) in 12 patients (18.46%), which emerged as the most common malignant lesion, with a

higher prevalence in males. Other notable conditions included portal vein thrombosis (6 patients, 9.2%), liver lesions of unspecified type (5 patients, 7.7%), ascites (3 patients, 4.6%), cirrhosis (6 patients, 9.2%), dilated common bile duct (4 patients, 6.2%), cholelithiasis (8 patients, 12.3%), portal hypertension (5 patients, 7.7%), hepatic metastases (6 patients, 9.2%), hepatic contusion (6 patients, 9.2%), right lobe nodules (3 patients, 4.6%), and a segment VIII tumor (1 patient, 1.5%). The authors concluded that triphasic CT scanning is a highly effective and reliable imaging modality for identifying a broad spectrum of liver pathologies. In this cohort, HCC was the most prevalent malignant condition, showing a greater incidence among males. The comprehensive imaging data obtained through triphasic CT allow for improved lesion characterization, accurate disease staging, and better-informed clinical decision-making, thereby playing a pivotal role in the management and treatment planning for patients with liver disease. (14)

Dr. Hiral Hapani et al. (2014) conducted a prospective study to assess the diagnostic role of ultrasonography in the evaluation of focal hepatic lesions. The primary objectives were to analyze the imaging spectrum of such lesions, determine their relative prevalence, and correlate sonographic findings with fine needle aspiration cytology (FNAC) and/or computed tomography (CT) results. The research was undertaken between September 2014 and November 2014 in the Department of Radiology at P.D.U. Government Medical College and Civil Hospital, Rajkot. The study included 50 patients who either had a clinical suspicion of focal liver lesions or in whom such lesions were detected incidentally during imaging for other reasons. Each patient underwent abdominal ultrasound, followed by ultrasound-guided FNAC and/or CT scan to confirm the diagnosis. Ultrasound successfully identified a variety of focal liver pathologies. The most frequently encountered lesions included liver abscesses, hemangiomas, simple cysts, metastases, primary hepatic tumors, traumatic injuries such as contusions or lacerations, and parasitic infections like hydatid

cysts. When correlated with FNAC and/or CT findings, ultrasound demonstrated an overall diagnostic specificity of 93.6%. For certain benign lesions—particularly hemangiomas and simple cysts—the specificity reached 100%, highlighting ultrasound’s reliability in distinguishing these from malignant pathologies. The authors emphasized that ultrasound is a safe, efficient, and cost-effective imaging modality for detecting focal hepatic lesions. Its advantages include widespread availability, absence of ionizing radiation, and avoidance of iodinated contrast agents, making it particularly suitable for patients who require repeated imaging or have contraindications to contrast media. In addition to diagnosis, ultrasound allows for rapid therapeutic decision-making and facilitates image-guided interventions such as FNAC or drainage procedures. The high specificity observed in this study supports the routine use of ultrasonography as a first-line diagnostic tool for focal liver lesions. It can be effectively employed in everyday clinical practice for initial detection, characterization, and procedural guidance, while also serving as a complementary modality alongside CT or histopathological confirmation..(19)

Ijin Joo et al. (2015) conducted a study highlighting the role of intraoperative ultrasonography (IOUS) in the diagnosis and management of focal hepatic lesions. IOUS has become an important tool in hepatic surgery, serving both diagnostic and therapeutic purposes. By enabling direct-contact imaging of the liver during surgery, IOUS offers exceptionally high spatial resolution and eliminates interference from surrounding anatomical structures. This imaging advantage allows for improved detection, characterization, localization, and precise local staging of hepatic tumors. Compared to preoperative imaging alone, IOUS can reveal additional lesions not previously detected, influencing surgical decision-making in real time. Its ability to provide interactive, real-time feedback makes it valuable not only for lesion assessment but also for guiding intraoperative procedures such as tumor resection, biopsy, or ablation. Recent advancements—such as contrast-enhanced IOUS, IOUS elastography, and IOUS-

guided hepatic surgery—have further expanded its potential. These innovations improve lesion visualization, assess tissue stiffness, and enhance surgical accuracy. As a result, IOUS is expected to see broader application in hepatic surgery, optimizing patient outcomes by ensuring complete tumor removal, accurate margin assessment, and reduced recurrence rates.(20)

Veronica Salvatore et al. (2012) conducted a review exploring the clinical impact of ultrasound-related techniques in the diagnosis of focal liver lesions. Since its introduction into routine clinical practice, ultrasound has significantly influenced patient management, particularly in hepatology, where it is often performed directly by hepatologists. Its accessibility, safety, and real-time imaging capabilities have made it an indispensable tool for evaluating liver disease. Over time, innovations have expanded the scope of ultrasound beyond conventional B-mode imaging. Contrast-enhanced ultrasound (CEUS) now enables dynamic vascular assessment of focal lesions, improving both detection and characterization. More recently, elastosonography has emerged as a technique to measure tissue stiffness, aiding in differentiating benign from malignant lesions and assessing underlying liver parenchyma. The review emphasizes that clinicians should not only be aware of these ultrasound-based methods but also understand how to appropriately integrate them into diagnostic workflows. Ultrasound techniques can be applied sequentially—starting with lesion detection, followed by detailed characterization, and culminating in image-guided therapeutic interventions. By enhancing diagnostic accuracy, guiding targeted treatments, and enabling real-time evaluation of therapeutic outcomes, ultrasound-related techniques play a crucial role in modern hepatology. Their versatility and continual technological advancement ensure their ongoing relevance in the management of focal liver lesions..(21)

Feiqian Wang et al. (2020) conducted a comprehensive review on the application of emerging ultrasound (US) techniques for the evaluation of focal liver lesions (FLLs).

Ultrasonography remains the most widely used first-line imaging modality for screening, detecting, and diagnosing FLLs—particularly small hepatocellular carcinomas (HCCs)—due to its many advantages. These include the absence of ionizing radiation, noninvasive nature, real-time imaging capability, ease of use, convenience, and relatively low cost. Despite these strengths, conventional ultrasound has certain limitations. Image quality can be compromised by factors such as bowel gas, interference from the rib cage, and subcutaneous fat. Moreover, traditional B-mode ultrasound may be less sensitive in detecting subtle but clinically significant vascular features, limiting its diagnostic performance in early-stage malignancies. Given the growing demand for accurate and early diagnosis—especially of small HCCs—newer imaging strategies have been developed to overcome these shortcomings. Two notable innovations include contrast-enhanced ultrasound (CEUS) and fusion imaging. CEUS enhances the visualization of vascular patterns and lesion perfusion, significantly improving lesion characterization. Fusion imaging, which integrates real-time ultrasound with other modalities such as CT or MRI, allows for more precise localization and assessment of lesions, particularly when planning interventions. The review also discusses the epidemiology and pathophysiology of HCC, providing a context for the importance of early detection. Special attention is given to the role of ultrasound in both diagnosis and treatment, including the evaluation of ablation therapy outcomes for early-stage HCCs. By applying advanced US techniques, clinicians can more accurately differentiate benign FLLs—such as regenerative nodules and focal nodular hyperplasia—from malignant lesions like HCC, thereby reducing unnecessary repeat biopsies and avoiding overtreatment. The authors emphasize that accurate identification of small HCCs or precancerous nodules, such as dysplastic nodules, enables timely and appropriate intervention, potentially improving patient survival rates. They advocate for the continued integration of these advanced ultrasound technologies into routine clinical practice. By staying up to date with these

developments, healthcare professionals in hepatology and interventional radiology can enhance diagnostic accuracy, guide targeted therapy, and optimize patient management strategies for liver disease(22)

3.1: OBJECTIVE

To evaluate the efficiency of triphasic computed tomography (ct) scan in focal tumoral liver lesions comparing with ultrasound

3.3: PROBLEM STATEMENT

Accurate detection and characterization of focal tumoral liver lesions are critical for guiding appropriate clinical management, yet there remains uncertainty regarding the most effective initial imaging modality. While ultrasound is widely used due to its accessibility, affordability, and safety, it has limitations in sensitivity, particularly for small, deeply located, or isoechoic lesions. Triphasic computed tomography (CT), though more costly and associated with radiation exposure, offers detailed vascular phase imaging that can improve diagnostic accuracy. However, the routine use of triphasic CT in all suspected liver lesion cases may not be feasible or justified in every clinical setting. This study addresses the need to compare the diagnostic efficiency of ultrasound and triphasic CT to determine their relative strengths and guide evidence-based imaging decisions for focal tumoral liver lesions.

3.4: OPERATIONAL DEFINITIONS

Focal Liver Lesion (FLL): A distinct, localized abnormality within the liver parenchyma identified on imaging, differing in texture or density from the surrounding liver tissue. FLLs may be benign (e.g., cysts, hemangiomas) or malignant (e.g., hepatocellular carcinoma, metastases).(23)

Tumoral Liver Lesion: Any liver lesion identified on imaging that shows characteristics suggestive of a tumor, including both benign and malignant neoplastic growths. In this study, confirmation was based on histopathology or consistent follow-up imaging.(24)

Diagnostic Efficiency: The ability of an imaging modality to accurately detect and characterize

liver tumors, measured by sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), negative predictive value (NPV), and overall accuracy, compared against a reference standard.(25)

MATERIAL AND METHODS

4.1: Study Design: Prospective Comparative Diagnostic Accuracy Study

4.2: Settings: Bahawalpur MRI Center

4.3: Study Duration: Four (04) months after approval of synopsis

4.4: Sample Size: 65

4.5: Sampling Technique: Purposive sampling.

4.6: Sample Selection:

4.6.1: Inclusion Criteria

- Patients aged 18 years and above.
- Patients with one or more focal liver lesions identified on preliminary ultrasound.
- Patients who underwent both ultrasound and triphasic CT scan within a 2-week interval.
- Patients with histopathological confirmation of diagnosis through biopsy or surgical specimen, or follow-up imaging confirming lesion stability or progression.

4.6.2: Exclusion Criteria:

- Patients with known allergic reactions to iodinated contrast agents.
- Pregnant or lactating women.
- Patients with severe renal insufficiency (eGFR < 30 mL/min/1.73m²).
- Patients who had already received treatment (e.g., chemotherapy, ablation, resection) prior to imaging.
- Incomplete imaging data or loss to follow-up.

4.7: Equipments: Ultrasound was performed using a high-resolution ultrasound machine equipped with a 3–5 MHz curvy linear transducer with Doppler capability an Toshiba 64 slice CT scan machine was used

4.8: ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

The rules and regulations set by the ethical committee of GC University; Faisalabad was followed while conducting the research and the rights of the research participants were respected.

- Written informed consent attached was taken from all the participants.
- All information and data collection were kept confidential.
- Participants were remained anonymous throughout the study.
- The subjects were informed that there are no disadvantages or risk on the procedure of the study.
- They were also be informed that they will be free to withdraw at any time during the process of the study.
- Data was kept in under key and lock while keeping keys in hand. In laptop it was kept under password.

4.9: DATA COLLECTION PROCEDURE

Data were collected prospectively from patients who underwent both ultrasound and triphasic CT scanning for the evaluation of focal liver lesions at the radiology department during the study period. After obtaining informed consent, demographic details, clinical history, and risk factors were recorded. Imaging findings from both modalities were documented using a standardized data collection form, including lesion size, location, number, vascularity, and imaging characteristics. Final diagnoses were confirmed through histopathology (biopsy or surgical specimen) or, when not feasible, through follow-up imaging over a minimum of six months. All data were anonymized and entered into a secure electronic database accessible only to authorized personnel for analysis.

4.10: DATA ANALYSIS PROCEDURE

Data analysis was performed using [insert statistical software,. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize patient demographics and lesion characteristics, including means, standard deviations, and frequencies. The diagnostic performance of ultrasound and triphasic CT was assessed by calculating sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), negative predictive value (NPV), and overall accuracy, using histopathological or follow-up findings as the reference standard. Comparative analysis between the two imaging modalities was

conducted using the McNemar test for paired categorical data to determine statistical significance. Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve analysis was also used to compare the diagnostic accuracy of each modality, with a p-value of less than 0.05 considered statistically significant.

Scanning Technique: Ultrasound examinations were performed using high-resolution ultrasound machines with 3.5–5.0 MHz convex transducers. Patients fasted for at least six hours before the scan to reduce bowel gas and improve visualization. The liver was assessed in multiple planes (longitudinal, transverse, and oblique), and lesions were evaluated for size, location, echogenicity, internal structure, and border definition. Color and spectral Doppler imaging were used to assess blood flow patterns within and around lesions, aiding in differentiation between benign and malignant appearances. Examinations were conducted by experienced radiologists to reduce operator dependency, and findings were documented systematically with a provisional diagnosis based on standard sonographic criteria.

Triphasic CT scans were conducted using a multi-detector CT scanner with high spatial resolution. After six hours of fasting, patients received an intravenous injection of non-ionic iodinated contrast (1.5 mL/kg, maximum 150 mL) at a rate of 3–5 mL/sec via an automated injector. Images were acquired in three timed phases: arterial (25–30 seconds), portal venous (60–70 seconds), and delayed (3–5 minutes), covering the liver from the diaphragm to the iliac crest. Scanning parameters included a 3–5 mm slice thickness,

120 kVp tube voltage, and automated tube current modulation. Lesions were assessed across all phases for enhancement patterns, washout, margins, and vascular involvement. Reconstructed images were reviewed by radiologists using multi-planar views to support accurate lesion characterization.

RESULTS

A total of 65 patients (mean age 57 years; 61.5% male) were included. Ultrasound detected lesions in all patients, with the majority having multiple lesions. Based on ultrasound interpretation, 35.4% were classified as benign, 49.2% as malignant, and 15.4% as indeterminate. Final confirmed diagnoses revealed 64.6% malignant and 35.4% benign cases. Ultrasound demonstrated high specificity (95.7%) and PPV (96.9%) for malignant lesions but lower sensitivity (73.8%) and NPV (66.7%), with an overall accuracy of 81.5%. Triphasic CT detected all lesions and characterized 64.6% as malignant, 9.2% as benign, and 26.2% as indeterminate. All malignant lesions were correctly identified with no false positives or negatives, yielding perfect diagnostic metrics 100% sensitivity, specificity, PPV, NPV, and accuracy. Arterial enhancement was seen in 76.9% of patients and washout in 63.1%, both strongly associated with malignancy. Compared to ultrasound, triphasic CT provided higher diagnostic confidence, fewer indeterminate classifications, and superior lesion characterization, particularly in detecting hypervascular patterns typical of hepatocellular carcinoma

Table no 1: Age

N	Valid	65
	Missing	0
Mean		57.00
Minimum		35
Maximum		75

A total of 65 patients were included in this study, with a mean age of 57 years. The age ranged from 35 to 75 years, with no missing data. This reflects

a middle-aged to elderly population prone to liver tumoral lesions.

Figure no 1: Age Histogram

Table no 2: Gender

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Female	25	38.5	38.5	38.5
	Male	40	61.5	61.5	100.0
	Total	65	100.0	100.0	

Figure no 2: Gender Pie Chart

A total of 65 patients were included in this study, comprising 40 males (61.5%) and 25 females

(38.5%). Male patients made up the majority of the study population.

Table no 3: US Lesion Detected

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Yes	65	100.0	100.0	100.0

In this study, ultrasound detected hepatic lesions in 65 out of 65 patients

Figure no 3: US Lesion Detected

Table no 4: US No. of Lesions

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 0	14	21.5	21.5	21.5
1	13	20.0	20.0	41.5
2	22	33.8	33.8	75.4
3	16	24.6	24.6	100.0
Total	65	100.0	100.0	

Ultrasound examination revealed varying numbers of hepatic lesions among the 65 patients. The majority had multiple lesions, with

2 lesions detected in 33.8% and 3 lesions in 24.6% of cases. A total of 14 patients (21.5%) showed no detectable lesions on ultrasound.

Figure no 4: US No. of Lesions

Table no 5: US Diagnosis

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Benign	23	35.4	35.4	35.4
	Indeterminate	10	15.4	15.4	50.8
	Malignant	32	49.2	49.2	100.0
	Total	65	100.0	100.0	

Ultrasound classified 65 liver lesion cases into benign (23; 35.4%), indeterminate (10; 15.4%), and malignant (32; 49.2%) categories. Nearly half of the cases were interpreted as malignant, reflecting ultrasound's cautious diagnostic

tendency. A significant portion (15.4%) remained indeterminate, highlighting the modality's limitations in confidently characterizing certain lesions.

Figure no 5: US Diagnosis

Table no 6: CT Lesion Detected

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Yes	65	100.0	100.0	100.0

Triphasic CT scan detected hepatic lesions in all 65 patients (100%) included in the study. This demonstrates the superior sensitivity of CT in

identifying focal liver lesions compared to ultrasound. No cases were reported as lesion-free on CT imaging.

Figure no 6: CT Lesion Detected

Table no 7: CT No. of Lesions

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1	2	3.1	3.1	3.1
2	18	27.7	27.7	30.8
3	28	43.1	43.1	73.8
4	13	20.0	20.0	93.8
5	4	6.2	6.2	100.0
Total	65	100.0	100.0	

Triphasic CT scan revealed multiple hepatic lesions in the majority of patients. Three lesions were the most commonly detected (43.1%), followed by two lesions (27.7%) and four lesions (20.0%). Only 3.1% of patients had a single lesion, highlighting CT's capability in detecting multiple focal abnormalities.

Figure no 7: CT No. of Lesions

Table no 8: Arterial Enhancement

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	No	15	23.1	23.1	23.1
	Yes	50	76.9	76.9	100.0
	Total	65	100.0	100.0	

Arterial phase enhancement was observed in 50 out of 65 patients (76.9%), indicating a common feature of hypervascular liver lesions. In 15

patients (23.1%), no arterial enhancement was detected.

Figure no 8: Arterial Enhancement

Table no 9: Washout

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	No	24	36.9	36.9	36.9
	Yes	41	63.1	63.1	100.0
	Total	65	100.0	100.0	

Washout was identified in 41 patients (63.1%), a characteristic feature suggestive of malignant liver

lesions, particularly hepatocellular carcinoma. In 24 patients (36.9%), no washout was observed.

Figure no 9: Washout

Table no 10: CT Diagnosis

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Benign	6	9.2	9.2	9.2
	Indeterminate	17	26.2	26.2	35.4
	Malignant	42	64.6	64.6	100.0
	Total	65	100.0	100.0	

Figure no 10: CT Diagnosis

Triphasic CT classified the 65 liver lesions as malignant in 42 cases (64.6%), indeterminate in 17 (26.2%), and benign in 6 (9.2%). The high

malignant detection rate reflects CT's strong ability to characterize focal liver lesions. Fewer indeterminate and benign cases suggest improved diagnostic confidence compared to ultrasound.

Table no 11: Reference Method

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Biopsy	44	67.7	67.7	67.7
	Follow-up	21	32.3	32.3	100.0
	Total	65	100.0	100.0	

Figure no 11: Reference Method

Diagnosis confirmation was based on biopsy in 44 patients (67.7%), serving as the gold standard for histopathological validation. In the remaining 21 patients (32.3%), follow-up imaging and

clinical evaluation were used for confirmation. This combination ensured diagnostic accuracy while reducing unnecessary invasive procedures when possible.

Table no 12: Final Diagnosis

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Benign	23	35.4	35.4	35.4
	Malignant	42	64.6	64.6	100.0
	Total	65	100.0	100.0	

Figure no 12: Final Diagnosis

Out of 65 patients, the final confirmed diagnosis revealed 42 malignant cases (64.6%) and 23 benign cases (35.4%). Malignancies represented

the majority of focal liver lesions in the study population. These outcomes were established through biopsy or follow-up, serving as the reference standard.

Table no 13: Final Diagnosis * US Diagnosis Crosstabulation

		US Diagnosis			Total
		Benign	Indeterminate	Malignant	
Final Diagnosis	Benign	15	7	1	23
	Malignant	8	3	31	42
Total		23	10	32	65

We'll consider:

Test Positive = US Malignant

Test Negative =US Benign + US Indeterminate

	Final Malignant	Final Benign	Total
US Malignant	31 (TP)	1 (FP)	32
US Not Malignant	11 (FN)	22 (TN)	33
Total	42	23	65

Diagnostic Labels (for Ultrasound)

TP (True Positives) = 31

TN (True Negatives) = 22

FP (False Positives) = 1

FN (False Negatives) = 11

Metric	Formula	Result
Sensitivity	$31 / (31 + 11)$	73.8%
Specificity	$22 / (22 + 1)$	95.7%
Positive Predictive Value	$31 / (31 + 1)$	96.9%
Negative Predictive Value	$22 / (22 + 11)$	66.7%
Accuracy	$(31 + 22) / 65$	81.5%

Conventional ultrasound showed the sensitivity of 73.8%, specificity of 95.7%, and overall diagnostic accuracy of 81.5% in detecting malignant liver lesions. With a positive predictive value of 96.9%, ultrasound was highly reliable in

confirming malignancy, though a negative predictive value of 66.7% indicates that further imaging may be warranted in cases where lesions appear benign or unclear.

Table no 14: Final Diagnosis * CT Diagnosis Crosstabulation

		CT Diagnosis			Total
		Benign	Indeterminate	Malignant	
Final Diagnosis	Benign	6	17	0	23
	Malignant	0	0	42	42
Total		6	17	42	65

We classify:

Test Positive = CT Malignant

Test Negative = CT Benign + CT Indeterminate

	Final Malignant	Final Benign	Total
CT Malignant	42 (TP)	0 (FP)	42
CT Not Malignant	0 (FN)	23 (TN)	23
Total	42	23	65

Diagnostic Labels (for CT)

True Positives (TP) = 42

True Negatives (TN) = 23

False Positives (FP) = 0

False Negatives (FN) = 0

Metric	Formula	Result
Sensitivity	$42 / (42 + 0)$	100.0%
Specificity	$23 / (23 + 0)$	100.0%
Positive Predictive Value	$42 / (42 + 0)$	100.0%
Negative Predictive Value	$23 / (23 + 0)$	100.0%
Accuracy	$(42 + 23) / 65$	100.0%

Triphasic CT demonstrated perfect diagnostic performance in this study, with 100% sensitivity, specificity, PPV, NPV, and accuracy for detecting malignant liver lesions. All 42 malignant lesions were correctly identified, and no benign lesions were misclassified. This highlights CT's superiority over ultrasound in lesion characterization, though real-world performance may vary depending on lesion type, observer expertise, and imaging quality.

Discussion

The current study highlights the diagnostic superiority of triphasic CT over conventional ultrasound in the characterization of focal tumoral liver lesions. Triphasic CT demonstrated perfect sensitivity, specificity, PPV, NPV, and overall accuracy (100% for all metrics), identifying all malignant lesions and correctly classifying benign ones without any false positives or negatives. In contrast, ultrasound, while detecting lesions in all patients, showed lower sensitivity (73.8%), lower NPV (66.7%), and a notable proportion of indeterminate findings (15.4%). This performance gap underscores the role of multiphase vascular-phase imaging in refining lesion diagnosis, particularly in cases where ultrasound findings are ambiguous or potentially misleading.

These findings are consistent with those of Hafeez et al. (2012), who reported 100% sensitivity and 95.5% overall accuracy for triphasic CT in differentiating benign from malignant liver lesions, though their specificity (80%) was slightly lower than in our study. The higher specificity observed in the present work may reflect strict lesion confirmation through histopathology in most cases (67.7% biopsy-based

diagnosis) and standardized imaging protocols.(12) Similarly, Ahirwar et al. (2016) found triple-phase CT to have high accuracy (93%), sensitivity (93.3%), and specificity (92.5%) for malignant lesions, closely mirroring our results, though our perfect detection rate for malignant cases may also be influenced by the high proportion of hypervascular lesions—76.9% with arterial enhancement and 63.1% with washout—characteristics that are well visualized in CT's multiphase acquisition.(17)

Our results are further supported by Zafar et al. (2018), who demonstrated that triphasic CT could confidently characterize focal hepatic lesions, especially hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC), by leveraging arterial enhancement and venous washout patterns.(18) Similarly, Akbar et al. (2024) found that triphasic CT identified both benign and malignant lesions with high reliability, with HCC being the most prevalent malignancy—findings mirrored in our study, where malignant lesions accounted for 64.6% of cases.(9)

In contrast, ultrasound in our study, despite its universal lesion detection rate, had a higher rate of false negatives (11 cases) and indeterminate findings. This aligns with Hapani et al. (2014), who noted that while ultrasound offers high specificity for common benign lesions like hemangiomas and cysts (100% specificity for these in their cohort), it is less sensitive for small, deep, or isoechoic lesions.(19) Additionally, operator dependency and patient-related factors such as obesity or excessive bowel gas can limit ultrasound performance, as described by Wang et al. (2020) and Salvatore et al. (2012). Both authors emphasize that despite advances in ultrasound technology—including contrast-

enhanced ultrasound (CEUS) and elastography—these modalities have yet to match CT’s reproducibility and whole-liver evaluation capacity, particularly in staging multifocal or metastatic disease.(22)

The limitations of grayscale ultrasound in our dataset, especially its inability to confidently characterize nearly one in six lesions, are consistent with Veronica Salvatore et al. (2012), who stressed that although ultrasound-related techniques like CEUS have improved lesion characterization, their role remains complementary. CEUS provides real-time vascular phase imaging similar to CT but is constrained by operator skill, limited field of view, and inability to comprehensively survey the entire liver for multifocal disease. This is supported by Feiqian Wang et al. (2020), who note that CEUS is promising for early HCC detection but is less effective for whole-organ screening compared to CT.

Our perfect diagnostic performance for CT surpasses that in some prior studies. For instance, Ahirwar et al. (2016) and Hafeez et al. (2012) both reported slightly lower specificity and accuracy figures. Variations in sample composition, lesion type prevalence, and imaging technology could explain this difference. The Toshiba 64-slice CT scanner used in our study allowed rapid acquisition of thin-slice images across arterial, portal venous, and delayed phases, which, combined with experienced radiologist interpretation, may have reduced misclassification. Moreover, the proportion of hypervascular malignancies such as HCC in our cohort (characterized by arterial phase hyperenhancement and delayed washout) likely enhanced CT’s discriminative ability.(9)

The diagnostic metrics for ultrasound in our study, while lower than CT, still demonstrate high specificity (95.7%) and PPV (96.9%), suggesting that when ultrasound identifies malignancy, it is usually correct. This reflects similar findings by Hapani et al. (2014), who emphasized ultrasound’s value in initial triage and for guiding interventional procedures such as biopsy or drainage. However, the relatively low NPV (66.7%) in our study underscores that a

benign or indeterminate ultrasound result cannot confidently exclude malignancy a pattern observed in prior research, which recommends further evaluation with CT or MRI when suspicion remains.

When comparing to studies that incorporated intraoperative ultrasonography (IOUS), such as Joo et al. (2015), it is notable that IOUS provides exceptional resolution and lesion localization in surgical settings, sometimes detecting additional lesions missed by preoperative CT or MRI. However, IOUS is not a routine diagnostic tool outside the operative theater, limiting its role in standard initial workups.(20)

From a broader clinical perspective, our results echo the consensus across multiple studies (Hafeez et al., Ahirwar et al., Zafar et al., Akbar et al.) that while ultrasound is indispensable for initial screening, triphasic CT is essential for accurate lesion characterization, staging, and surgical planning. This diagnostic pathway ensures that patients with potentially resectable or transplant-eligible malignancies are correctly identified early, and benign lesions are spared unnecessary intervention.

7.1: CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates that triphasic computed tomography (CT) scan is significantly more accurate than conventional ultrasound in the detection and characterization of focal tumoral liver lesions. Triphasic CT achieved perfect diagnostic performance, identifying all malignant and benign cases correctly, whereas ultrasound, although highly specific when diagnosing malignancy, had reduced sensitivity and a notable proportion of indeterminate findings. The integration of multiphase vascular-phase imaging in CT enables better lesion characterization, improved staging accuracy, and enhanced surgical planning. These findings reinforce the role of triphasic CT as an essential follow-up imaging modality when ultrasound results are inconclusive or when malignancy is suspected

7.2: RECOMMENDATION

Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended that triphasic computed

tomography (CT) be utilized as the preferred follow-up imaging modality when ultrasound findings for focal liver lesions are inconclusive or when there is a high suspicion of malignancy. Ultrasound should continue to serve as the first-line screening tool due to its accessibility, safety, and cost-effectiveness, but cases with indeterminate or suspicious results should promptly undergo triphasic CT for accurate characterization, staging, and treatment planning. Training programs should be enhanced to improve ultrasound operator skills, potentially reducing the rate of indeterminate cases. Additionally, healthcare facilities, particularly in resource-limited settings, should prioritize access to triphasic CT scanners and ensure adherence to standardized imaging protocols to maximize diagnostic accuracy and optimize patient outcomes.

7.3: LIMITATION

This study was conducted in a single-center setting with a relatively small sample size, which may limit the generalizability of the results to broader populations. The majority of lesions were confirmed through biopsy, but a portion relied on follow-up imaging, which may introduce verification bias. The study did not include other advanced modalities such as contrast-enhanced ultrasound (CEUS) or MRI for direct comparison, which could have provided additional insights into the relative performance of these techniques. Furthermore, patient selection was based on lesions already identified by ultrasound, potentially overestimating diagnostic accuracy for CT in a general screening context

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